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NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity, and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: <http://www.NAUTILOS-h2020.eu>.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present **Brokerage Events Meeting Protocols** deliverable (D11.3) represents a record of types and number of contacts established during high profile marine industry events, identified by NAUTILOS consortium to introduce the project's innovative technology to the market, reaching potential customers and users. Related to Task 11.1 of WP11 "Exploitation and Impact", the brokerage events are an essential component of NAUTILOS exploitation strategy marketing engagement since their main objective is to trigger interest among oceanography stakeholders, such as industrial and marine technology companies, universities and research centres, to subsequently employ the revolutionary, cost-effective instrumentation for ocean observation, developed within the scope of the project.

In summary, the report comprises the following structure:

- Context
- Methodology
 - Overview of attended events
 - Meeting Protocols structure
- Meetings Protocols
 - Brokerage Events
 - Brokerage Opportunities
- Conclusion

In addition to keeping record of the types of established contacts, the report contains the types of expressed interest towards exploitation, per each represented technology during these events, with remarks for follow up engagement activities in some instances. This deliverable is organic to NAUTILOS Exploitation Strategy (D11.1 and D11.7), as the brokerage events represent an insightful experience for partners where they could gain a better understanding of the main points of potential clients, enabling them to adopt a demand driven, customer centric approach in the business plan development of the project by tailoring the respective unique value positions to closely resonate with their clients' specific needs.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
CD	Communication and Dissemination
DG MARE	Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research & Innovation
GA	Grant Agreement
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
REA	Research Executive Agency
TIM	Technical and Innovation Manager
RTD	Research and Technology Development
TechOceanS	Technologies for Ocean Sensing
UN	United Nations
UVP	Unique Value Proposition

I. CONTEXT

The brokerage events of NAUTILOS are deemed a prerequisite for the successful commercialization strategy for the project's Key Exploitable Results since they present an excellent opportunity for introducing the new technology and engage with interested stakeholders and potential customers of NAUTILOS innovative sensors and samplers for observation of the Ocean. The events are part of Task 11.1 *Exploitation Strategy and Campaign*, which main objective is to guide the development of feasible exploitation routes for all identified KERs, in cooperation with partners, foster their deployment at European and international scale along with ensuring the long-term availability of the cost-effective sensors and the sustainability of the concepts developed within NAUTILOS.

The ultimate goal of the brokerage events is to provide information and exchange on the state of play of the solutions developed within the project, in the backdrop of the already available technology in the sector as a whole, to foster future collaborations and motivate subsequent exploitation of the outputs. The insights gained during the interactions with stakeholders are considered relevant for the update of each instrument's business plan, with refined marketing messaging and strategies, and tailored to the customer needs unique value proposition so that the time to conversion is shortened. The audience groups that the events are targeting are professionals from the marine industries, institutions' research and development departments as well as ocean data end-users.

NAUTILOS partners who are technology producers, sensor and sampler owners respectively, were the ones mostly attending NAUTILOS brokerage events, drawing on the innovative instrumentation's cost-effectiveness, interoperability, possible maintenance saving, sustainability and performance in relation to the existing market alternatives, highlighting the competitive nature of the NAUTILOS solutions.

II. METHODOLOGY

The events proposed by the project's Exploitation Team to partners to present NAUTILOS instruments as well as other project's outputs, such as citizen science initiatives or policy briefs for supporting ocean observations, were of great scale and significance to the marine industry, academia, NGOs and decision makers involved in the fostering of a sustainable blue economy and promoting the conservation of the marine ecosystem. They were assessed as having legitimate potential for establishing beneficial business contacts and partnerships for future collaborations, and also for the subsequent market realization of NAUTILOS technology. Additionally, they were seen as an excellent platform to learn more about the attendees and other commercial exhibitors' interests, needs and know-how, while increasing the visibility of NAUTILOS results and positioning them on top of minds of industry leaders and executives when

it comes to investing in innovative, cost-effective solutions demanded by the realities in the sector.

A thorough methodology for collecting relevant event data from participating partners was co-developed by CEiiA as WP11 leader, and EP as the beneficiary responsible for compiling the brokerage event meetings' protocols (D11.3). These records would be useful in delineating the big picture of the industry segments where most interest was expressed from, the size and geographical location of the companies, type of technology, and partnerships or business models, they were looking to utilize, potential investment interest and so on. Consequently, this could serve as a blueprint for the development of a customized to the respective instrument business plan, as part of the final exploitation strategy of the project.

1.1 OVERVIEW OF ATTENDED EVENTS

Per NAUTILOS Grant Agreement, the consortium was required to engage in two brokerage events, which was exceeded as a target. Depending on the scale of NAUTILOS members' representations and types of results showcased, the brokerage methodology differentiates between **brokerage events** and **brokerage opportunities**. The former are related to occurrences considered to be of larger impact for KER's exploitation, involving a bigger number of technology partners attending and the latter regard mostly networking experiences, enhancing the visibility of the project and its outputs.

It is noteworthy that the two events deemed most relevant by WP11 Exploitation team, in terms of outcomes and further exploitation interactions, were the UN Ocean Decade and European Maritime Day. NAUTILOS partners involvement in them was planned by CEiiA, EP and EurOcean. As leader of WP10 "Communication, Dissemination and Outreach", EurOcean provided WP11 with unwavering creative, logistics and coordination support during these events' implementation, which further enhanced the visibility of the project's efforts towards making use of the results and their commercialization.

Table 1 provides an overview of the brokerage events and opportunities.

Table 1. Brokerage Events Overview

Number and Name of the Event	NAUTILOS partners involved
Brokerage Event 1 Ocean Race Grand Finale - Genoa, Italy, 27 – 30 June 2023	CEiiA, ETT, CNR - ISMAR
Brokerage Event 2 MATS 2023 - Southampton, UK, November 2023	AQUATEC
Brokerage Opportunity Ocean Sciences Meeting - New Orleans, February 2024	AQUATEC, NKE, CNR - IRBIM
Brokerage Opportunity Matchmaking event @ European Ocean Days, Brussels, March 2024	CEiiA
Brokerage Event 3 OCEANOLOGY International 2024, London, UK, 12-14_March 2024	CEiiA, AQUATEC, NKE, SubCtech, Edgelab, HCMR
Brokerage Event 4 UN Ocean Decade Conference 2024, 10 - 12 April, Barcelona, Spain	CEiiA, EurOcean
Brokerage Event 5 European Maritime Day 2024, Svendborg, Denmark, 30 - 31 May 2024	CEiiA, EurOcean, SubCTech

1.2 MEETING PROTOCOLS' STRUCTURE

The protocols of the meetings that were conducted with potential customers, and the established contacts, follow a uniform structure, with the same type of information collected from partners through a tool specifically developed for this purpose by EP and CEiiA. Some pieces of data such as 'name of company', 'name of contact' and 'email address' were considered by some consortium members sensitive private information and therefore inappropriate to be

shared with the consortium and the public so they were left as optional fields to be filled in. The other components of the protocols' structure are quite general and do not constitute proprietary information. For the purpose of this public deliverable, even if provided by partners, personal information as names and individual's e-mail is not included here. This information is however stored in a master table in the project's shared repository, so that direct follow up interactions are catered to, until the end of the project. Owing to the B2B and networking nature of these brokerage events, the information collected was voluntarily provided, mostly shared through an exchange of business cards and public social media profiles. Data was obtained for the purposes of a follow up connection with parties who showed a specific interest in learning more about NAUTILOS work and technology, and who explicitly requested additional information on the project. All individuals were assured of NAUTILOS commitment to treating personal data with ethical responsibility, with no disclosure to the external to the consortium parties.

Figure 1. Illustration of the Brokerage Event Information Collection Tool

Event's name & link /Name of attending partner	Instruments presented or other results	Company (optional)	Category university, research institution, NGO, professional association, SME, industry, investor, policy maker, other (specify)	Name of Contact optional	Business Department sales, marketing, R&D, Business Development, CEO, Senior Management, Technical Manager, Other (specify)	E-mail (optional, general email would do too)	Comments on expressed interest general product's information, foster collaborations for future research/projects, scaling up, industrialization, knowledge transfer, patent selling, other (specify)	Next steps	NAUTILOS POC
European Ocean Days, 4 - 8 March, Brussels, Belgium <i>A matchmaking session for Charter action partners was held back-to-back with the forum on 4 March. This event was an opportunity to network with EU Mission projects, philanthropists and Charter signatories</i>									
https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/governance/european-ocean-days_en									
CEiIA									Catarina Lemos

The elements of the Meeting Protocol are as follows:

- Event's name and link/ Name of attending partner (includes brief description of the event)
- Instruments presented or other results
- Name of Company (**Optional**)
- Category of the company (university, research institution, NGO, professional association, SME, industry, investor, policy maker, other (specify))
- Name of contact (**Optional**)
- Business Department (Sales, Marketing, R&D, Business Development, CEO, Senior Management, Technical Manager, other (specify))
- Email address (**Optional**)
- Comments on expressed interest (general product's information, foster collaborations for future research/projects, scaling up, industrialization, knowledge transfer, patent selling, something else (please specify))

- Next steps
- NAUTILOS point of contact
- Communication support

The development of the methodology and table tool was incremental and resulted from a collaborative effort from all WP11. As a learning experience based on partners content sharing availability, responsiveness and received feedback, it was continuously revised, improved and updated. Reminder emails aiming to facilitate the compilation of data from the events in a timely fashion were sent periodically by the Technology Innovation Manager (TIM) and EP to all partners involved.

In addition to the master Information Collection Tool (Figure 1), for the EMD specifically, CEiiA, with a team of 2 people, has developed a separate table enabling real time feeding of contacts and expressed interest per sensor/sampler. The table was shared with all NAUTILOS members attending the EMD, electronically via Google forms and on tablet, in full compliance with the rules of the event for no paper participation. This supplementary tool, available only for the EMD, was essential in securing both quick and smooth processing of incoming contact data during a dynamic tempo and volume of interactions. The collected information was later on transferred to the master contact database stored on the project's Google Drive.

III. MEETINGS PROTOCOLS

Meetings Protocols for each event are compiled based on the information provided by partners through the above-mentioned methodology and tools.

3.1 *EVENTS*

3.1.1 OCEAN RACE GRAND FINALE, GENOA

a. Brief description

The Ocean Race Grand Finale (<https://www.theoceanrace.com/en/route/genova>) took place in Genoa from 27 to 30 June 2023. It is a world-known professional sporting event, sailing's toughest team challenge and one of the sport's Big Three events, alongside the Olympic Games and America's Cup. Back-to-back with it, a week-long series of talks and workshops took place addressing critical themes related to sustainability, the blue economy, smart cities, and citizen science, to include a "B2B Ocean Race 2023" event organized by the Italian Chamber of Commerce on June 30th. This networking event brought together companies, public and private actors for opening up new business opportunities.

NAUTILOS Technology Innovation Manager, Catarina Rasquilha Lemos, Centre of Engineering and Product Development, CEiiA attended the event and introduced to interested contacts the new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers for ocean observation developed within the project.

b. Attending partners

CEiA, ETT, CNR – ISMAR, EurOcean

c. Instruments presented and other results

Marketing materials, information on CEiA animal tag – commercial leaflet.

d. Name (**Optional**) and category of Company, Contact Name (**Optional**) and email, Business Department, Comments on expressed interest, next steps

Contact names and individual email addresses are collected in the project's database created specifically for the Brokerage Events and are not listed in this public deliverable for personal data protection considerations.

Name of Company	Category / Sector	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
The Ocean Race			Expressed interest in a microplastic sensor with less need of filters cleaning and maintenance	Get more information from the sensors related to the microplastic sampling and quantification and reach back to Stefan.	CEiiA
Red Sea Global	Industry		General interest in NAUTILOS and what the project does. With regard to sensors – interest in the CTD and CEiiA's Animal Tag	Send a general info email about the project, CTD and animal tag.	CEiiA
Pluscargo Brasil	Professional Association		This Brazilian association focus on international logistics. However, they are willing to know more about NAUTILOS project as it can be of interest for their network.	Send a general email about the project.	CEiiA
Estofados Atlanticos	SME		No particular express as this companies focus on marine upholstery fabric solutions. However, they are willing to know more about NAUTILOS project as it can be of interest for their network.		CEiiA
ETT SOLUTIONS	SME		Francesco is part of NAUTILOS consortium; Discussion about data sharing.	name and email available in project's database	CEiiA

Move Viaggi Societa Benefit	SME		Travel agency, no particular interest.		CEiiA
NAVALCARE –	SME		This Brazilian company focus on developing sensors for vessels - fire, sinking, accelerometer, so they have interest to understand NAUTILOS instrumentation, mainly those that can be installed in vessels.	Send a general email about the project, with all project results. SHARE OIAR.	CEiiA
ECOTEC	Industry		Various interests in respect to: plastic pyrolysis for oil/fuel on ships, onboard composting for feed and general ship modernization.	Send a general email about the project.	
BRIZO	Industry		This Italian company focuses on developing a low-cost water sports tracker. It was mentioned that we will share OIAR with them. They have interest to understand NAUTILOS project.	Send a general email about the project, with all project results. Add to OIAR.	
Oengineering	Industry			Send a general email about the project, with all project results.	
WSENSE	SME		This Italian company focuses on unleashing the power of underwater wireless communication for blue economy. It was mentioned that we will share OIAR with them. They have interest to understand NAUTILOS instrumentation.	Send a general email about the project, with all project results.	

e. Communication support

This event was promoted on NAUTILOS Social Media Channels – LinkedIn, Facebook and X and reposted by CEiiA and other partners.

Figure 2. NAUTILOS participation in the B2B event promoted on LinkedIn

In addition to the B2B event, NAUTILOS partners took part in a full day of discussions and presentations dedicated to the exploration of “Low-Cost/Cost-Effective Technologies for Ocean Data Monitoring and Participatory Initiatives,” during which the project unveiled a policy brief titled “Empowering Citizens Through Ocean Knowledge Co-production.” The document is an important output of NAUTILOS as it underscores the pivotal role of the ocean in the Earth’s system and emphasises the importance of understanding and managing it sustainably, with a focus on citizen science.

Figure 3. NAUTILOS Policy Briefs unveiled during Ocean Race Grand Finale Genoa

Policy Brief No. 1 Empowering Citizens Through Ocean Knowledge Co-production

Policy Brief No. 2 Supporting Ocean Observations To Address Climate Change

As part of WP10 Communication and Dissemination Outreach, another signature event organized during the Ocean race was the Policy Round Table where a second policy brief titled “Supporting Ocean Observations to Address Climate Change” was presented. Although not qualified as a typical B2B encounters, many high-level contacts were established during these events, to include representatives of the European Commission’s Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (EC – DG MARE) and the Healthy Oceans and Seas, RTD – DG. The launch of the policy briefs and the round table were profoundly covered in NAUTILOS digital channels with a website news publication, a dedicated press release, reposts on social networks and posts on partners’ social accounts. Highlights from the events and more details can be found in the respective WP10 deliverable D10.3.

3.1.2 MARINE AUTONOMY AND TECHNOLOGY SHOWCASE 2023 (MATS)

a. Brief description

The Marine Autonomy & Technology Showcase (MATS, <https://noc-events.co.uk/mats-2023>) was created by UK’s National Oceanography Centre (NOC) as an exciting way to showcase the world-leading platform and sensor developments across the sector engaging many stakeholder groups from both the private and public sector, all united around the benefits that can be achieved from development and use of marine autonomy for ocean observation.

MATS is an annual event hosting an international audience of presenters and attendees. It aims to explore the information needs of users of Marine Autonomous Systems (MAS), review the current technologies available to enable the data gathering for MAS users and explore the methods of taking that data and making it exploitable information for the user need. The 2023 edition took place in Southampton, UK from 7 to 9 November 2023.

b. Attending partners

AQUATEC attended the event at a joint stand of +All ATLANTIC Cluster of EU funded projects - TechOcean & George projects.

c. Instruments presented and other results

AQUATEC presented their Click and Sound Recorder along with NAUTILOS branded commercial flyers of the Click and Sound Recorder. CEiiA's Animal Tag flyers were distributed to visitors and contacts as well. Additionally, the project had a poster on display, promoting NAUTILOS sensors and samplers developed by partners, with key technical parameters and a QR code leading the audience to the Sensor and Sampler page on NAUTILOS website, where more detailed and practical information is available.

a.

- d. Name (**Optional**) and category of Company, Contact Name (**Optional**) and email, Business Department, Comments on expressed interest, next steps

Most of the NAUTILOS related discussions regarded expressed interest in the AQUATEC's Subsea Sound and Click Recorder, which was still in development at the time. Some were also related to other products that AQUATEC manufactures. A number of people took pictures of the posters and scanned the QR codes.

e. Communication support

This event was promoted on NAUTILOS Social Media Channels – LinkedIn, Facebook and X and reposted on some of the partners’ social accounts. NAUTILOS promotional materials were also available for dissemination. NAUTILOS branded commercial flyers representing the technologies provides for a coherent look and strengthens NAUTILOS brand positioning.

3.1.3 OCEANOLOGY INTERNATIONAL

a. Brief description

Oceanology International (<https://www.oceanologyinternational.com/london/en-gb.html>) is the leading forum where industry, academia and government share knowledge and connect with the world’s marine science and ocean technology communities. In 2024 it was conducted from 12 to 14 March in London, UK and featured a three-day conference and exhibition, welcoming over 8,000 attendees and enabling more than 500 exhibitors to showcase the latest ocean technologies and developments, indoors and outdoors on water demos and vessels.

b. Attending partners

NKE booth; AQUATEC booth with a poster showcasing results of the passive acoustic sensor + sensor showcased; SCT – booth, NAUTILOS leaflets + sensors brochure.

Partners attending the event as visitors: Federico Pensa, Edgelab; Manolis Ntoumas, HCMR and João Fortuna & Daniel Costa, CEiiA

c. Instruments presented and other results

NKE - WiSens;

AQUATEC - a poster showcasing results of the passive acoustic sensor and the sensor showcased along with NAUTILOS branded flyers of the sensor;

SubCTech booth with NAUTILOS project leaflets and NAUTILOS branded sensor flyers;

The focus of the partners attending as visitors was to promote NAUTILOS technologies (through the designed NAUTILOS leaflets) to relative exhibitors and establish contacts with sea technology providers.

d. Name (**Optional**) and category of Company, Contact Name (**Optional**) and email, Business Department, Comments on expressed interest, next steps

Name of Company	Category / Sector	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
CSIS	University	Departamento de Acústica	general interest in NAUTILOS and specific interest in the microplastic sampler		SubCTech
SeaBird inc NORTEK Saiv Aanderaa Teledyne, Daowan Technology Co	SME	Contacts were predominantly established with the Technical Managers	Interest was expressed in general product's information as well as possibilities to foster collaborations for future research projects. Proposed intercomparison experiments with NAUTILOS instrumentation		HCMR
AML Oceanographic	Industry	Business Development	Would be interested in studying the possibility of incorporating the CTD in its current packages if it's worth it when it is done	Reach out once we have a finished product to show	Daniel Costa, CEiiA
DEVELOGIC GmbH	Industry	Sales & Marketing	Was interested in knowing more about CEiiA's Lander platform	Stay in touch over time for when opportunities arise	João Fortuna, CEiiA
Dartmouth Ocean Technologies	Industry	Senior Management	Was interested in the project overall and would be open to discuss future opportunities related to eDNA	Stay in touch over time for when eDNA opportunities arise	João Fortuna, CEiiA
eDNAtec	Industry	Business Development	Was interested in the work done by Nautilus and the possibility of eDNA monitoring in future projects	Stay in touch over time for when eDNA opportunities arise	Daniel Costa, CEiiA

NKE reported to have achieved an impressive 120 contacts in total, with about 40 of them showing keen interest in the WiSens solutions, including NAUTILOS sensors (Do and Chl-A). The majority of contacts made were with entities within the fisheries and environmental studies sectors, through their scientific and R&D staff, reflecting the strategic importance and high-level appeal of NAUTILOS technologies in the maritime industry.

NKE highlighted a particular interaction with a Belgium distributor who was interested in testing sensors, namely NKE's DO and Chl-A sensors developed within NAUTILOS.

Figure 4. AQUATEC's booth

Figure 5. NKE's booth

e. Communication Support

Two social media posts on NAUTILOS page, reposts by partners on their personal accounts.

3.1.4 UN OCEAN DECADE CONFERENCE 2024

a. Brief description

The 2024 Ocean Decade Conference was held under the motto of 'delivering the science we need for the ocean we want' in the city of Barcelona from 10 - 12 April 2024. It brought together the global Ocean Decade community and partners to celebrate and take stock of progress and set

joint priorities for the future. The conference was the highlight of an entire Ocean Decade Week having taken place from 8 - 12 April 2024.

The event covered the full range of Ocean Decade Challenges including critical issues such as climate change, food security, sustainable management of biodiversity, sustainable ocean economy, pollution and natural hazards.

b. Attending partners

CEiiA, EurOcean, CNR, ETT S.p.A

c. Instruments presented and other results

“All Atlantic” sister projects shared a booth where NAUTILOS was presented by EUROcean and CEiiA. NAUTILOS promotional materials were distributed along with displaying CEiiA’s ‘Mantaa’ animal tag with dissolved oxygen sensor and a leaflet promoting the Open Access Marine Instrumentation Roadmap survey.

Figure 6. CEiiA and EurOcean representing NAUTILOS at All Atlantic booth

Under the lead of EurOcean, leaders of WP10 Communication, Dissemination and Outreach, NAUTILOS co-hosted a Satellite Event complementing the conference, entitled "Beyond Climate Change: Sustained Observation in Support of the Blue Economy" on the 9th of April, at the Museum of Natural Science of Barcelona. The event focused on three key themes: (1) data-driven decision-making: exploring how ocean data enhances sustainable resource management and the blue economy. Strategies for effective data integration will be shared; (2) public-private synergy: highlighting collaboration between sectors for continuous ocean observation and blue growth;

and (3) global collaboration: sharing best practices and tech advancements for international cooperation in ocean observation.

During this landmark event, NAUTILOS proudly unveiled its last policy brief titled “Beyond Climate Change, Sustained Observation in Support of the Blue Economy”, which brought the project to the attention of a broader group of conference participants, leading to more visitors at the shared booth, eager to learn more about NAUTILOS and the sensors and samplers it develops, for an impact on climate change.

Figure 7. Promoting NAUTILOS participation in the event on social media.

Figure 8. NAUTILOS Project Coordinator Gabriele Pieri presenting at the event

- d. Name (**Optional**) and category of Company, Contact Name (**Optional**) and email, Business Department, Comments on expressed interest, next steps

Name of Company	Category / Sector	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
BIMS	NGO	Development Director and Program Director	Several common interests related to CEiiA tags, mostly because as a group they have divers. Also interest in sampling and landers.	Send an email about CEiiA tags and lander, including general information about the project and its results.	CEiiA
DOSI	NGO		General interest in the project and results.	Send email with additional information.	CEiiA
University of Plymouth	Research Institution	Marine Scientist and National Geographic Explorer.	As a National Geographic Explorer she uses tags, so she wants to know more about it.	Send an email about NAUTILOS tags, including general information about the project and its results.	CEiiA
University of Porto / CIIMAR	Research Institution	Professor (UP); Head of the Aquatic Biodiversity and Conservation group at (CIIMAR)	Research interests focus on ecology and marine biodiversity. Interest in understanding NAUTILOS instrumentation.	Send a general email about the project.	CEiiA
Institut de Recherches Halieutiques et Océanologiques du Bénin	Research Institution	Oceanographer	He works on the field of oceanography. It was mentioned that we will share OIAR with them. She has interest to understand NAUTILOS instrumentation.	Send a general email about the project, with all project results.	CEiiA
SATLINK	SME	Business Development	This panish technology company focus focused on the development of Internet of Things (IoT) and end-to-end (E2E) connectivity solutions. It was mentioned that we will share OIAR with them. They	Send a general email about the project, with all project results.	CEiiA

			have interest to understand NAUTILOS instrumentation.		
Senckenberg Research Institute and Natural History Museum Frankfurt/M.	Research Institution	Head of the Department of Marine Zoology, Head of the Crustacea Section, Head of the Ichthyology Section, Professor of Special Zoology at the Goethe University Frankfurt/M.	Not specified	Send a general email about the project, with all project results.	CEiiA
Plymouth Marine Laboratory	Research Institution	Head of Marketing & Communications	It was mentioned that we will share OIAR with them.	Send a general email about the project, with all project results.	CEiiA
Harvard University	Research Institution	Researcher	She works on the field of bioinspired engineering. It was mentioned that we will share OIAR with them. She has interest to understand NAUTILOS instrumentation.	Send a general email about the project, with all project results.	CEiiA
Galapagos National Park	Other	Director	Part of Galapagos' community and biodiversity Team (Galapagos National Park Directorate (GNPD), MigraMar, Charles Darwin Foundation (CDF), Fundación Jocotoco and Universidad San Francisco de Quito (USFQ)).	Send an email about NAUTILOS tags, including general information about the project and its results.	CEiiA

Jocotoco	Foundation	Marine Coordinator, Galápagos Program.	Part of Galapagos' community and biodiversity Team (Galapagos National Park Directorate (GNPD), MigraMar, Charles Darwin Foundation (CDF), Fundación Jocotoco and Universidad San Francisco de Quito (USFQ)).	Send an email about NAUTILOS tags, including general information about the project and its results.	CEiiA
Universidad San Francisco de Quito	University	Professor	Part of Galapagos' community and biodiversity Team (Galapagos National Park Directorate (GNPD), MigraMar, Charles Darwin Foundation (CDF), Fundación Jocotoco and Universidad San Francisco de Quito (USFQ)).	Send an email about NAUTILOS tags, including general information about the project and its results.	CEiiA
Charles Darwin Foundation	Research Institution	Investigator - Marine Biodiversity Research	Part of Galapagos' community and biodiversity Team (Galapagos National Park Directorate (GNPD), MigraMar, Charles Darwin Foundation (CDF), Fundación Jocotoco and Universidad San Francisco de Quito (USFQ)). Contact is a HSE part IV commercial diver, a Scientific Diver and PADI instructor and has dedicated her career to the conservation of marine ecosystems.	Send an email about NAUTILOS tags, including general information about the project and its results.	CEiiA
Charles Darwin Foundation	Research Institution	Researcher; diver	Main focus is to assess the effectiveness of the Galapagos Marine Reserve in protecting shark populations, and to conduct research that leads to the development of effective management	Send an email about NAUTILOS tags, including general information about the project and its results.	

			plans for sharks in Galapagos and wider region.		
Charles Darwin Foundation	Research Institution	Investigator - Sea Turtle Conservation	They have funding for acquiring tags.	Send an email about NAUTILOS tags, including general information about the project and its results.	
Equipe Cafeína/OxeanHub	Other	Brasil	This Brazilian team focuses on raising awareness for blue economy, in general, in Bahia. Focus on microplastics. They have interest to understand NAUTILOS instrumentation.	Send a general email about the project, with all project results with focus on microplastics solutions.	
ISCIA/Consultant	Consultant	Professor - Ports and Logistics; consultant	As part of ISCIA - Institute of Information and Administration Science, and Ports and logistics teaching, he is willing to know more about NAUTILOS project as it can be of interest to their network.	Send a general email about the project, with all project results.	
Seavoice	Other	Journalist; Cultural Heritage Framework Programme; University of Edinburgh	As journalist for Seavoice, she shared the opportunity to publish a document about NAUTILOS project.	Discuss a possible publication about NAUTILOS project within WP10.	

e. Communication Support

The event enjoyed intense communication support, both in NAUTILOS own digital channels (1 website news post, 11 posts on Linked-In, 10 posts on Facebook and 11 on X) and partners' accounts resharing the information or with their original posts, tagging the project.

Figure 9. NAUTILOS at UN Ocean Decade Conference - a tweet

3.1.5 EUROPEAN MARITIME DAY 2024 (EMD)

a. Brief description

The European Maritime Day (EMD) is the annual EU meeting point on maritime affairs and sustainable blue growth, and the place where ‘Ocean Leaders Meet’ as the slogan goes. EMD 2024 was held in Copenhagen, Denmark, 29 – 31 May. It was assessed by the Exploitation team as the most prominent brokerage engagement event for the project since it has a history of having enabled many project partnerships and co-operations among stakeholders, and has also contributed to getting the need of sustainable management of ocean resources higher on the EU’s agenda. In addition to business contacts, it gives NAUTILOS an exposure to EU policy and decision makers as a champion for more investments in ocean observation initiatives, pivotal in Europe and the world’s quest for a resilient, circular economy.

The European Maritime Day gives participants, to include NAUTILOS representatives, the opportunity to keep abreast with the latest projects and achievements in the maritime domain, to establish new partnerships and gain insights into the latest EU priorities regarding the European Maritime Policy and funding.

b. Attending partners

CEiiA, EurOcean, SubCTech

c. Instruments presented and other results

NAUTILOS participated in the EMD with a booth where partners had the animal tag by CEiiA and parts of SubCTech's Submersible Sampler for Nano- and Microplastics (SuNaMips) exhibited. The entire collection of NAUTILOS sensors and samplers was promoted through NAUTILOS branded flyers and other creative elements within the booth, such as a 3D cardboard box, a cylinder table and candy jar featuring the QR code to NAUTILOS Sensor/Sampler page on project's website. NAUTILOS videos and e-modules from the Summer School were played on a TV screen, attracting visitors and triggering genuine interest in the project and its results.

Figure 10. On the right: Sensor leaflets. On the left: tablets displaying digital information related to the sensors - website, Google Forms survey for contact collection

EMD 2024 – NAUTILOS Booth

- d. Name (**Optional**) and category of Company, Contact Name (**Optional**) and email, Business Department, Comments on expressed interest, next steps

More than 50 contacts were established with companies and organizations from various domains and interests. A summarized information is presented below while the detailed database containing names and emails is stored in the project's shared repository. Due to the larger number of established contacts, the records are grouped by category, for better comprehension.

Contacts from the category of **Industry** are all from Denmark:

Name of Company	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
INDUSTRY				
Blue atlas robotics	R&D and Business Development	Expressed interest: general project information, Open Access Marine Instrumentation Roadmap (OAIR), MAANTA (CEiiA).	<u>Other interests:</u> Marine robotics	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Sternula	R&D, Business Development and Marketing	General project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects, Open Access Marine Instrumentation Roadmap (OAIR), MAANTA (CEiiA), WiSens TD - Chl-a (NKE), WiSens TD - DO (NKE).	<u>Other interests:</u> First commercial provider of affordable, secure and global connectivity for the maritime industry using the new AIS 2.0 standard, also known as the "VHF Data Exchange System" (VDES). AIS 2.0 VDES vs Traditional AIS.	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao

Contacts from the category of **Consultancy** (Denmark and Portugal):

Name of Company	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
CONSULTANCY				
Generalisten ApS	Business Development	General project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects, WiSens TD - DO (NKE), WiSens TD - Chl-a (NKE).	<u>Other interests:</u> New technologies for ship industry.	Catarina Lemos and Ines Brandao, CEiiA
PNO Innovation Portugal	R&D and Business Development	General project information, foster collaborations for future research/ projects, Fluorometric DO Sensor (HESSO), Deep Ocean Radioactivity Sensor (HCMR), WiSens TD - Chl-a (NKE), Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT), Deep Ocean CTD Sensor (UL-FE), AQUAscat Mk2 (AQUATEC), WiSens TD - DO (NKE), Marine animal-borne temperature-salinity-DO Tag (CNRS), Silicate Electrochemical Sensor (NKE), MAANTA (CEiiA), Click & Sound Recorder (AQUATEC)	<u>Other interests:</u> Innovation - Public Funding.	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao

Contacts from the category of **Government Institution** (Denmark, Portugal):

Name of Company	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
GOVERNMENT INSTITUTION				
Danish geodata agency	R&D, Technical Manager.	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects, Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT).	<u>Other interests:</u> Improve bathymetric coverage of Denmark	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Department of housing (local government and heritage)	R&D, Technical Manager.	general project information, AQUAscet Mk2 (AQUATEC), MAANTA (CEiiA), Click & Sound Recorder (AQUATEC)		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
The Finnish transport and communications agency traficom	R&D.	general project information, MAANTA (CEiiA)	<u>Other interests:</u> Marine Biology.	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
DanPilot	Technical Manager	general project information	Other interests: Dredging Operations	

Contacts from the category of other **Institution** (Denmark, Portugal, Ireland, Belgium, Latvia, France):

Name of Company	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUILOS
INSTITUTION				
Expertise France	R&D, Business Development and Marketing departments	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects	Other interests: Maritime Safety and Security.	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Kimo	R&D	general project information, Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT), MAANTA (CEiiA).	Other interests: Marine Litter	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
DGPM - Directorate general for maritime policy	R&D	general project information		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Câmara municipal Torres vedras	R&D	general project information, MAANTA (CEiiA).	Other interests: Coastal Management	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
+Atlantic colab	R&D	general project information	Other interests: Low-cost technologies for water monitoring	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Danish Maritime Authority	Business Development	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao

Ministeriet for fodevarer landbrug og fiskeri	Business Development	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects, MAANTA (CEiiA), Marine animal-borne temperature-salinity-DO Tag (CNRS).		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Allied Irish Banks.	- R&D	general project information		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Seaglow	R&D, Business Development	general project information, MAANTA (CEiiA), Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT)	Energy Transition - Plastic Event for SCT	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Latvian Hydroecology Institute	R&D	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects	Other interests: Underwater research of benthic habitats in the Baltic Sea	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
UVisionResearch	R&D	general project information		Jana Fahning
Atlantic Cities	CEO, R&D	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects	Other interests: Coastal Tourism	Jana Fahning
Blue bio alliance	Technical Manager	general project information	Other interests: Blue bio resources	Catarina Lemos
Technopôle Brest-Iroise	R&D	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects		Catarina Lemos

Contacts from the category of **Research** (Denmark, Portugal, Belgium, Austria, Germany, Spain, Norway, Latvia)

Name of Company	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUILOS
RESEARCH				
Ciimar	R&D	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects	<u>Other interests:</u> Marine Sciences; Renewables energies (<i>new field of interest</i>)	Catarina Lemos and Ines Brandao, CEiiA
DLR	R&D	general project information, Deep Ocean Radioactivity Sensor (HCMR), Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT).		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
BlueBio Alliance	R&D, Technical Manager	general project information.	<u>Other interests:</u> Blue bio resources	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
JPI oceans	R&D, Technical Manager.	general project information, patent selling; Deep Ocean Radioactivity Sensor (HCMR), Marine animal-borne temperature-salinity-DO Tag (CNRS), MAANTA (CEiiA).		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
N(n)le international business and economic development center	R&D, Business Development	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Expertise France ESIWA	R&D, Business Development	general project information, foster collaborations for future	<u>Other interests:</u> Maritime Safety and Security.	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao

		research/projects, Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT).		
Hereon - Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon	R&D	general project information, MAANTA (CEiiA).	<u>Other interests:</u> eDNA Sampling.	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
CIM - Centro de Investigação Marina – Vigo	R&D	general project information, Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT), MAANTA (CEiiA).	<u>Other interests:</u> Marine Geology	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Norce	R&D	general project information	Other interests: Aquaculture	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Sea teach	Technical Manager	general project information		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Sun & blue congress	R&D	general project information, Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT)	<u>Other interests:</u> Coastal Tourism.	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Latvia Research	R&D	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects	Other interests: Underwater research of benthic habitats in the Baltic Sea	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
CNR - ISMAR – Bologna	R&D	general project information		Jana Fahning
AVL	R&D	general project information		Jana Fahning

Contacts from the category of **SME** (Denmark):

Name of Company	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
SME				
INILAB	CEO	general project information, Open Access Marine Instrumentation Roadmap (OAIR), foster collaborations for future research/projects, Knowledge transfer, Fluorometric DO Sensor (HESSO), Deep Ocean Radioactivity Sensor (HCMR), WiSens TD - Chl-a (NKE), Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT), Deep Ocean CTD Sensor (UL-FE), AQUAscet Mk2 (AQUATEC), WiSens TD - DO (NKE), Marine animal-borne temperature-salinity-DO Tag (CNRS), Silicate Electrochemical Sensor (NKE), MAANTA (CEiiA), Click & Sound Recorder (AQUATEC).		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao

Contacts from the category of **Professional Association** (Denmark):

Name of Company	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION				
Miwire group aps	Senior Management, Sales.	general project information, Open Access Marine Instrumentation Roadmap (OAIR).	<u>Other interests:</u> Maritime Safety and Security.	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Flowpoint	CEO, Technical Manager.	general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects	<u>Other interests:</u> Maritime Safety and Security	Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao
Bionic System Solutions	R&D	: general project information, foster collaborations for future research/projects	<u>Other interests:</u> Bionic Systems.	Catarina Lemos/Inês Brandão

Miscellaneous category (Denmark):

Name of Company	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
STAMP Reklamefoto Aps (Photograph)	Marketing	general project information		Catarina Lemos, Ines Brandao

A graphic illustration of the expressed interest in NAUTILOS technology per organization's sector is presented below:

Figure 11. Interest based on organization's sector

e. Communication Support

The event was promoted on NAUTILOS social channels (Linked-In, Facebook and X) as well as on attending partners' social accounts, with reposts or project tags.

3.2 OPPORTUNITIES

3.2.1 OCEAN SCIENCES MEETING

a. Brief description

The Ocean Sciences Meeting (OSM) is a central conference connecting the ocean community to share findings and advance the impact of science. The event in 2024 was held from 18 to 23 February in New Orleans, USA. The meeting welcomed almost 6,000 attendees from various organizations, educators, scientists, journalists, policymakers and students, unified by the common goal to establish global partnerships and collaborations that are empowering a more renewable tomorrow.

b. Attending partners

AQUATEC, NKE, CNR – IRBIM

c. Instruments presented or other results

AQUATEC had a poster showcasing results of the passive broadband marine mammal sound and underwater soundscape recorder.

CNR-IRBIM revealed NAUTILOS results related to the demonstration involving AdriFOOS as testing platform for the new Dissolved Oxygen and Chlorophyll-a sensors and the receiver WiHub, both developed within the project.

NKE – WiSens TD-DO and WiSens TD-Chl-a

d. Name (Optional) and category of Company, Contact Name (Optional) and email, Business Department, Comments on expressed interest, next steps

Name of Company	Category / Sector	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
FVON network	research institutions + SMEs	Coordinator	the group is very interested in the DO sensor developments – purchasing the sensor for research projects	https://fvon.org/ Next steps: share NAUTILOS public deliverables	Michela Martinelli Damien Malardé, Yves Dégrés

For NKE, Ocean Sciences Meeting was an extremely interesting event with relevant interactions. They achieved impressive contacts overall, with some showing keen interest in the NAUTILOS sensors (DO and Chl-A sensors). The interested contacts were senior scientists, in charge of operational projects, reflecting the strategic importance and high-level appeal of NAUTILOS technologies in the oceanographic instrumentation, including even opportunities to apply those for additional demonstrations projects with international funding.

NKE highlight a particular interaction with **FVON consortium** (ODN+ NOAA + IPMA + CCMAR + CNR) – an international consortium that has the objective to develop embedded instrumentation on fishing vessels to collect data at sea, and especially in coastal areas. Among FVON consortium of American and European organizations is the Environmental Defense Fund that flagged interest in potentially supporting NKE on future demonstrations with fishing vessels in United States of America, namely with NAUTILOS NKE DO and Chl-A dataloggers used on WiHub Solution. This is considered a great opportunity as it holds potential for Europe to join the instrumentation contributors in a field where only New Zealand and USA technologies are considered currently. NKE are excited to be part of shaping a new future for data collection where oceanographic data can be collected from the ocean using fisheries activities without any impact on them (as data can be automatically recovered).

e. Communication Support

The event was promoted on NAUTILOS social channels (Linked-In, FaceBook and X) as well as on attending partners' social accounts.

NAUTILOS @NAUTILOS_H2020 · Feb 28

...

Last week's Ocean Sciences Meeting in New Orleans was an absolute highlight for #Nautilus!
 Our partners, @nke_instruments and @Cnrlrbim were featuring a range of NAUTILOS sensors, and talks on ocean observation applications!

#OceanScience #OceanTechnology #OceanObservation

3.2.2 EUROPEAN OCEAN DAYS

a. Brief description

From March 4th to 8th, the European Commission organized for the first time in Brussels, Belgium a week of events dedicated to European maritime topics regarding the future priorities for Europe's Seas, blue innovation, investment opportunities as well as ocean literacy activities.

b. Attending partners

CEiiA

c. Instruments presented or other results

Paulo Figueiredo attended the matchmaking event organized on March 4 for the opportunity to network with other EU mission Ocean projects and to potentially make new contacts with investors. Additionally, NAUTILOS e-poster, prepared and submitted by WP10 lead EurOcean, was played during the 2nd Annual Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters Forum on March 5th.

d. Name (Optional) and category of Company, Contact Name (Optional) and email, Business Department, Comments on expressed interest, next step

Name of Company	Business Department of contact	Expressed Interest	Next steps/Remarks	POC from NAUTILOS
INDUSTRY				
BIVALVIA - mussel startup.		Might have interest in some sensors. However, they are just starting their business (TRL7). http://www.udensmalas.lv , Latvia		Paulo Figueriedo
The Seaweed Company, The Netherlands.	Project Manager, Project CEO	http://www.theseaweedcompany.com	They produce seaweed and manage several hectares of it. They use sensors to monitor the seaweed (TRL9).	Paulo Figueriedo
AKROCEAN	Project Manager	they provide in-situ metocean and environmental data collection at sea by integrating sensors into their buoys.	https://www.akrocean.com/	Paulo Figueriedo
Cerberus Seaweed Systems, Germany	Co-founder	to create the possibility of cultivating algae as a resource that is economically valuable and ecologically compatible in Europe.	https://www.cerberus-seaweedsystems.com	Paulo Figueriedo
EcoSeaNova, Switzerland		they build algae ropes and use sensors to monitor the algae	https://ecoseanova.esperglabal.com	Paulo Figueriedo
INALVE, France	CEO	they develop microalgae cultivation technology	http://www.inalve.com	Paulo Figueriedo

Maral Tehcnologies, Croatia	CEO	as a spin-off of a mature mechanical engineering company, MARAL TECHNOLOGIES is dedicated to providing premium equipment for mariculture		Paulo Figueriedo
Ocean Access	CEO	they have developed a submersible buoy designed for remote underwater monitoring and subsea communication purposes	https://www.oceanaccess.no/	Paulo Figueriedo
SeaReenergy Offshore Holding GmbH & Cie., Germany	Project IT Manager	they provide services to the wind energy sector, helping companies become carbon neutral. They use sensors in their solutions.	https://www.searenergy.com	Paulo Figueriedo
Underwater Gardens International, Spain	Executive President & Founder	they provide monitoring solutions for sea gardens, utilizing sensors in these solutions.	https://www.underwatergardens.com/	Paulo Figueriedo
VisionAnchor, Spain	Chief Innovation Officer	the FLORA project aims to develop and demonstrate an industrial-scale prototype of a multi-purpose ocean station, named the FLORA Ocean Station (or FLORA O.S.), which will have capabilities for renewable energy generation and operational oceanography. Equipped with a novel	https://wedglobal.com/projects/	Paulo Figueriedo

		sensor suite that includes radar, the FLORA O.S. will be designed as a low-environmental-impact system crucial for bird and biodiversity data acquisition, supporting Marine Spatial Planning (MSP).		
Framework Robotics, Germany	CEO, Sales Manager	they have maritime robotics, including AUVs (Autonomous Underwater Vehicles), ROVs (Remotely Operated Vehicles), ROTVs (Remotely Operated Towed Vehicles) and incorporate sensors in their equipment.	http://www.fw-robotics.de	Paulo Figueriedo

3.2.3 OTHER

AQUATEC have reported on two additional brokerage events they had participated in to promote the Passive sound recorder and click recorder developed within NAUTILOS. Contacts arising from these opportunities are shown in the table below:

H2O & COVE Demo Day, Halifax & Dartmouth Nova Scotia, June 2023

Company	Country	Role	Interest
Oceanographic Instruments	Canada	General Manager and Business Development Manager	General Interest
Survey Company	UK	Managing Director	Acoustic survey
Dredging instrumentation	UK	Director	Dredge monitoring
Community College	Canada	Researcher	Broad monitoring project
Floating Desalination Plants	Canada	Employee	General interest
Oceanographic Instruments	Canada	Sales Rep	General interest
Oceanographic Instruments	Canada	Sales Rep	General interest

IV. CONCLUSION

The purpose of the Brokerage Events Meeting Protocols deliverable is to provide a record of what was presented at these events as well as to build a database of contacts which could be used in the follow up exploitation/business plan per sensor/sampler, in the identification of the buyer/user persona as well as the unique value proposition (UVP) definition and subsequent marketing communication accompanying the go-to-market activities. In line with the latter, the document does not have the ambition to render an analysis of the events themselves, partners' involvement and initiative, or lack thereof, or an assessment of the interest expressed in a particular sensor. Conspicuous challenges along the way were first, from the plethora of marine events, to discern those that were worth attending with regard to gaining benefits for the future commercialization of NAUTILOS outputs. Second, to commit partners to attend with the objective of showcasing key project results – the necessary groundwork for their further utilization by the industry. The leadership role of the Technology Innovation Manager, EP, and EurOcean as communication lead (WP10), was indispensable in encouraging participation, instilling enthusiasm and highlighting the importance of collecting the relevant information.

NAUTILOS partners engaged in a total of 5 large scale brokerage events where they presented the innovative cost-effective technologies for underwater ocean observation, and two smaller scale, referred to in this deliverable as brokerage opportunities. In addition to introducing the novel marine instrumentation in the quest for commercialization, partners showcased many intellectual outputs that are of equal significance for driving positive change in the realm of climate crisis and resilient blue economy. NAUTILOS' championing for investing more effort, assets and visionary approaches in the ocean variables monitoring and data collection incurred policy makers' attention and was further enhanced by the numerous citizen science campaigns that the project partners had conducted.

Regardless of magnitude, brokerage events are considered a powerful medium for networking and gaining allies on the lookout for new knowledge exchange or exploitation partnerships, They are the ultimate scene setter for future collaborations, scientific progress sharing and capacity building, all motivated by the Ocean's community common goal – to preserve our blue planet's resources for the future generations.

APPENDIX 1: PHOTO GALLERY

EMD 2024

New Approach To Underwater Technologies For Innovative, Low-Cost Ocean Observation

AdriFOOS

Testing platform for new Dissolved Oxygen and Chlorophyll- α sensors + receiver WiHub developed within H2020 NAUTILOS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000825 (NAUTILOS). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any views that may be made of the information contained therein.

OCEAN SCIENCES MEETING

MATS 2023

OCEAN RACE GENOA 2023

UN OCEAN DECADE 2024

OCEANOLOGY INTERNATIONAL 2024

APPENDIX 2: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

Deliverable 11.3 was developed in accordance with the provisions outlined in the following related documents:

- NAUTILOS Grant Agreement,
- NAUTILOS Consortium Agreement Nr. 101000825.
- NAUTILOS Exploitation Strategy

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	NAUTILOS Grant Agreement	NAUTILOS repository
2	NAUTILOS Consortium Agreement Nr. 101000825.	NAUTILOS repository
3	NAUTILOS Exploitation Strategy D11.1, D11.7	NAUTILOS repository